

Synthesis of Schiff Bases and Thiazolidinones bearing 2,4'-Bithiazole Moiety

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THIAZOLES¹, (2,4'-bithiazole)-2'-amine-4-aryl², Schiff bases³ and 4-thiazolidinones⁴ are known to possess various biological activities. Therefore, it was thought worthwhile to synthesise these classes of compounds from (2,4'-bithiazole)-2'-amine-4-aryl and evaluate their antibacterial activities.

The compounds were tested for antibacterial activity against *E. coli*, *S. abony*, *S. aureus* and *P. aeruginosa* using cup-plate method in acetone medium (0.5% concentration), and the activity was compared with furazolidone⁶ as standard. The results reveal that

- a ; X=Y=H
 b ; X=H, Y=Cl
 c ; X=H, Y=CH₃
 d ; X=H, Y=OCH₃
 e ; X=Cl, Y=H
 f ; X=Y=Cl
 g ; X=Cl, Y=CH₃
 h ; X=Cl, Y=OCH₃
 i ; X=CH₃, Y=H
 j ; X=CH₃, Y=Cl
 k ; X=Y=CH₃
 l ; X=CH₃, Y=OCH₃
 m ; X=OCH₃, Y=H
 n ; X=OCH₃, Y=Cl
 o ; X=OCH₃, Y=CH₃
 p ; X=Y=OCH₃

Scheme 1

the Schiff bases containing 2,4'-bithiazole moiety are less active than the standard against *E. coli* and *S. abony* and are inactive against the other two organisms. Compounds 3 showed comparable activity with that of the standard against *S. aureus*, but 4 were more active than the standard against *P. aeruginosa* and less active against other organisms.

Experimental

All melting points were determined in open capillary and are uncorrected. The purity of compounds was checked by tlc on silica gel. Ir spectra (KBr) were recorded on a Perkin-Elmer 781 spectrophotometer, mass spectra on a AEI MS 902 spectrometer and nmr spectra on a FT-NMR (80 MHz) instrument.

(2,4'-Bithiazole)-2'-amine-4-aryl (1) were prepared by known method².

(2,4' - Bithiazole) - 2' - arylideneamino-4-aryl (2). *General procedure*: A mixture of 1 (0.01 mol) and benzaldehyde (0.012 mol) in anhydrous benzene (50 ml) was refluxed on a water-bath using Dean-Stark water separator for 6-7 h. Excess benzene was then distilled off and the resulting solid was dried and crystallised from benzene-acetone (1 : 1): 2a m.p. 148°, b 169°, c 146°, d 187°, e 128°, f 156°, g 178°, h 158°, i 151°, j 170°, k 183°, l 174°, m 122°, n 114°, o 135°, p 129°; ν_{\max} (KBr) 1 620 (C=N), 1 605, 1 530, 1 460 and 1 430 cm^{-1} (phenyl and aryl ring vibrations); 2j M^+ 395; δ (80 MHz; CDCl_3) 2.94 (3H, s, CH_3) and 7.36-7.98 (1H, m, Ar, N=CH, thiazole).

3-[4''-Aryl-(2'',4'-bithiazole)-2'-yl]-2-aryl-4-thiazolidinone (3). *General procedure*: A mixture of 2 (0.01 mol) and mercaptoacetic acid (0.012 mol) in anhydrous benzene (50 ml) was refluxed on a water-bath using Dean-Stark water separator for 7-8 h. Excess benzene was then distilled off and the resulting viscous liquid was washed with 10% sodium carbonate solution to remove any unreacted mercaptoacetic acid. The product separated was filtered, washed with water, dried and crystallised from benzene-acetone (1 : 1): 3a m.p. 206°, b 205°, c 187°, d 197°, e 258°, f 213°, g 254° h 191°, i 221°, j 174°, k 192°, l 224°, m 193°, n 184°, o 257°, p 201°; ν_{\max} (KBr) 1 690 (C=O) and 1 590 cm^{-1} (C=N); 3j M^+ 469; δ (80 MHz; CDCl_3) 2.54 (3H, s, CH_3), 4.3 (2H, s, CH_2), 6.6 (1H, s, CH) and 7.15-7.84 (10H, m, Ar and thiazole).

3-[4''-Aryl-(2'',4'-bithiazole)-2'-yl]-2-aryl-5-methyl-4-thiazolidinone (4). *General procedure*: A mixture of 2 (0.01 mol) and thiolactic acid (0.012 mol) in anhydrous benzene (50 ml) was refluxed on a water-bath using Dean-Stark water separator for 7-8 h. Excess benzene was then distilled off and the resulting viscous liquid was washed with 10% sodium carbonate solution to remove the unreacted acid. The product separated was filtered, washed with water, dried and crystallised from benzene-acetone (1 : 1) to yield the products (50-65%): 4a m.p. 177°, b 189°,

c 175°, d 174°, e 273°, f 186°, g 184°, h 195°, i 186°, j 190°, k 197°, l 203°, m 186°, n 153°, o 253°, p 195°; ν_{\max} (KBr) 1 690 (C=O) and 1 595 cm^{-1} (C=N); 4j M^+ 483; δ (80 MHz; CDCl_3) 1.71 (3H, d, CH-CH_3), 2.36 (3H, s, CH_3), 4.4 (1H, q, CH), 6.5 (1H, s, CH) and 7.41-7.93 (10H, m, Ar and thiazole).

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